

Title: Quintessential Cryptocurrency Ecosystem Components

Name: Steven Dryall

Affiliation: FinTECH Circle, London, UK

INTRODUCTION:

Cryptocurrency ecosystem deployment requires the understanding of many subjects both technical and social. Creation of a viable cryptocurrency ecosystem requires careful management of concurrent developmental efforts. This presentation will provide an overview of the requisite components for a viable cryptocurrency ecosystem.

AIM:

To show the requisite components of a viable cryptocurrency ecosystem. Deployment of the components outlined will result in a viable ecosystem.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Incipient Industries has been involved with cryptocurrency development since the company was founded. Direct involvement with numerous cryptocurrency projects has lead to a proven method and system for the creation of a viable cryptocurrency ecosystem. Using open-source solutions combined with requisite tools it is possible to consistently create a cryptocurrency ecosystem with longevity and value.

RESULTS:

Incipient Industries has been successful in the creation and deployment of cryptocurrency ecosystems. According to market valuations by leading industry sources, projects created by Incipient Industries have increased consistently from initiation to high multipliers. ROI is consistently assured.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of these efforts, the deployment of a viable cryptocurrency ecosystem is replicable using these methods.

KEYWORDS:

bitcoin, cryptocurrency, digital money, ecosystem, decentralized, network

BIOGRAPHY:

Steven Dryall is the Principal of Incipient Industries and a Founding Director of Nikola Tesla Unite Ltd. Steven was certified by The Royal Canadian Mint for “contributing to the evolution of currency”.

Steven is a digital money strategist, deployment expert and thought leader. A direct contributor to some of the most important technological developments in our society relating to digital media, digital marketing and digital money. A technology pioneer with a deep, long background in the creation and distribution of digital goods and services.

Steven is currently working on changing the essence of economics using cryptocurrency and blockchain technology.